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A STUDY ON THE FATIGUE CHARACTERISTICS OF SINGLE LAP JOINT BETWEEN CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTIC/CARBON STEEL

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Introduction

- In order to meet the requirements of the fuel efficiency regulations, various studies on the weight reduction of vehicles are being conducted
- Especially, many researchers tried to achieve the vehicle weight reduction by applying lightweight materials, e.g. Aluminum, Magnesium, plastics, etc.
- To introduce **Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP)**, lightweight and have high mechanical properties-to-weight ratio, into vehicle parts together with traditional materials like carbon steel, **structural adhesives** are often used to bond them
- In order to ensure the reliability of such components with different materials, *long-term properties such as material degradation and fatigue life as well as short-term properties like adhesive strength*, should be considered

➤ ***Fatigue characteristics according to surface roughness***

Preparation of test specimens and test methods

- Lap shear specimens were made with S45C steel and CFRP prepreg joined using L-F501, epoxy based adhesive tape
- CFRP prepreg and adhesive tape were cured together during the process, under 10 MPa, 150°C for 30 min
- Fatigue tests were conducted using MTS 810 universal testing machine

Surface treatment and results

- Steel surfaces were sand blasted using Al_2O_3 abrasive with air pressure of 5 bar
- Abrasives with three different particle sizes were used to obtain different levels of surface roughness

Grit size	#14	#60	#180
Particle diameter (μm)	1190	250	88
Surface roughness, R_a (μm)	4.156	1.786	0.560
Surface observation after sand blasting			

Fatigue test results

- The smaller the particle size, the lower the surface roughness and the fatigue life increased under the same stress level
- Abrasives with large particle sizes can reduce fatigue life by leaving unremoved oxide films on steel surface

Grit size #14

Grit size #60

Grit size #180

Conclusion

- The effect of surface roughness on the fatigue life of carbon steel-CFRP joints is studied
- Three different types of abrasives with different particle sizes were used to obtain different levels of surface roughness
- The smaller the particle size, the lower the surface roughness and the fatigue life increased under the same stress level
- Abrasives with large particle sizes can reduce fatigue life by leaving unremoved oxide films on steel surface

Thank you for your attention

